

Cultural Transformation and Resurrection in Manju Kapur's Immigrant

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Abstract :

Nina, a lecturer, is 30 years old, unmarried, and stays with her mother in Delhi in Manju Kapur's novel *Immigrant* (2009). She marries Ananda, an N.R.I. doctor, and moves to Canada as a newlywed bride. In this story, the author depicts the life of a married woman living alone in an alien nation where Indian culture and individualism have long been alien concepts. The central focus is on marital pleasure, women's role at home, and their attitude change. The Indian bride in Canada is a phase in the butterfly's life cycle when it starts to lose its colour. There is loneliness and a feel of being uprooted from one's surroundings, with only a husband to converse with. Nina's personality and mental state have completely changed by the end of the novel. She had a fresh outlook on life and began working on a new career and job.

Keywords: Attitude, Career, Focus, Individualism, Loneliness, Marital, Personality, Uprooted.

Introduction

Manju Kapur is a well-known Indian author. She stands out among her generation's writers with five highly praised novels: *Difficult Daughters*, *A Married Woman*, *Home*, *The Immigrant*, and *Custody*. *Difficult Daughters* earned her the coveted Commonwealth Award for debut fiction from the Asian area in 1999. *The Immigrant* was shortlisted for the DSC Prize, while *A Married Woman* was shortlisted for the Hutch Crossword Prize for fiction. The primary topic of diaspora and immigrant concerns is addressed in *Immigrant*. A contemporary writer with contemporary ideas and perspectives, term 'Diaspora' comes from the Greek word 'Diaspora,' which means 'dispersion.' Diaspora is the spread of people, language, or culture that was once concentrated in a single location. Every immigrant who has relocated to different nations throughout the world in search of better fortunes is referred to as diasporic. These migrants keep a strong sense of attachment to their previous home with them wherever they move. Diaspora examines displacement or dislocation, as well as intergenerational conflict and cultural identity. *Immigrant* spirits are frequently discovered to be split. The focus of the study is on how Manju Kapur's characters in her novel attempt to establish their identity as Indian diasporas in the United States, despite their divided souls. The novel begins in the 1970s with Nina, a thirty-year-old unhappy English instructor who lives in New Delhi with her widowed mother. Nina's mother wants her to marry an NRI and move to a different country. Nina is unsure of herself and in desperate need of a new home. Meanwhile, Ananda Sharma, a Canadian NRI dentist, approaches her with a proposition. Nina quits her profession as a teacher, marries Ananada, and relocates to Canada to escape her mother's and societal constraints. Ananada is a new immigrant who has settled into life in Canada gradually. Since he is on his way to complete the link, he marries Nina. Ananda is also one of these victims, because his stay in his uncle's house when he visits Canada

for the first time elucidates his estrangement and anguish to us. He was complimented for his excellence in accomplishing things and for being so excellent when he was a youngster. In Canada, on the other hand, his uncle tells him to be polite, clean the bathroom, and do all of his chores by himself. Even his close relative did not consider him as a privileged individual. Ananda has learned how people and life are in a new area throughout time. He takes life for granted, begins to act and dress like a Canadian, and becomes acquainted with the clothing, cuisine, and people. However, he is a culture-conscious Indian who values his heritage. Though he has the chance to meet Sue, a Canadian woman, she pressures him into having a physical connection, but he resists, and even when his masculinity is called into question, he maintains his values. As a result of this encounter, he decides to find a companion from his nation. He wants a female from his homeland and culture with whom he can identify, and who will not dominate or challenge his manhood in the way that the Canadian lady did. Ananada's nervousness causes him to marry Nina, a charming Indian woman, in need of a firm grasp, a comforting friend to help him survive in an unknown circle. When a bride marries an NRI, she travels to a faraway country with high hopes, but when the aeroplane takes off, many things in her life take a turn she never expected. Nina is no exception to this diasporic phenomenon. It is not a myth that every easterner in the western world is mistreated. Slavery had been abolished for centuries before Abraham Lincoln battled for its abolition. He did not want the southern people to be enslaved, therefore he fought and won the civil war. Of fact, the south is not enslaved, but the eastern spirit is degraded in the west. Although the cause of prejudice may be based on race, colour, or nationality, unfairness and injustice have persisted for millennia. When Nina, the heroine, arrives in Toronto, she finds herself in this scenario. An investigation takes place at the immigration clearance desk, where she is asked a series of

questions regarding her possessions and is viewed suspiciously. She becomes restless and embarrassed, and for the first time, she feels lonely with her silent spouse at her side. She eventually asks Ananda why they don't treat a European or an American the same way, and why this only occurs to her. When diasporic individuals begin their lives in a distant place, they may face tyranny and intolerance. This type of incident causes the immigrant to forget their identity in order to live in their new nation. When compared to Nina, Ananda finds it easier to reach agreements and concessions. As the days pass, Ananda alters his name and requests that everyone refer to him as 'Andy.' Nina is much like the caged bird. As she is exposed to different people, environments, languages, and foods, her dissatisfaction leads to solitude. Nina is taken to Ananda's uncle's place for supper and to make her feel at ease. Ananda never compels her to dress in a western way; he admires her and wishes for her to wear traditionally. Nina is also at ease in a sari and jewellery, and she is confident in her own skin. Sue and Garry admire her attractiveness, but Ananada's uncle, who is of Indian descent, taunts her, making her feel like a "fish out of water" situation. After all of this, the diasporic sensibility is finely tuned throughout the storyline of the novel to produce a harmonious melody. Nina's rage and her battle against the odds come to a satisfying climax. Nina begins to dress in jeans and a t-shirt in order to get to know people and her surroundings. Despite the fact that she is uncomfortable in her western dress, she refuses to abandon the new style and arrive. She misplaced her individuality and most prized culture in order to make friends and survive. Bird at home Nina has a number of issues to deal with in her new surroundings. Even after adjusting her perspective, she is still unable to persuade others and acquire respect. She was known as a speaker prior to her marriage, but things have changed in her new location. She is no longer known as a professor; she is now known as Nina Sharma, rather than by her personality. Sue advises her to get out of her non-working and disrespectful situation by enrolling in a two-year Library Science course. However, Nina's economic independence brings with it a slew of other internal challenges. Apart from the migration concerns, the couple's family life, culture, and marital faithfulness are all put to the test in an unfamiliar environment. Indians are recognised for their high regard for morality and ethics, but their perspective shifts when they travel abroad. People's values degrade when they are introduced to new situations. They fail to recognise that their mindset dictates that they live to please everyone, and as a result, they lose their personality and become a perfect illustration of 'survival of the fittest.' Both Nina and Ananda fail to appreciate their marriage. Neither of them misses a chance to be disloyal to the

other. Ananda fails to meet Nina's bodily requirements in the early stages of their marriage. His incapacity is concealed by falsehoods. He never does anything to fill the void in his marriage. Instead, he flirts with Mandy and loves her company. Nina had a similar experience when she meets Anton, a New Yorker who never misses a chance to appreciate and gratify Nina. That's the ruse, and it's

working on her. The connection appears platonic at first, but as Nina becomes more interested in the new world and adventures, she forgets about herself and loves cigarette smoking, beer, and all of the bar activities like a Canadian. Nina becomes confined as a result, and she surrenders herself to Anton more as a way of experiencing the difference and establishing her independence. She doesn't show even a smidgeon of regret. When she tries to leave his relationship, she is raped by Anton, and Nina is stunned and does not respond further. Nina's desire for independence and freedom caused her to trust others readily. Nina's abrupt switch to non-vegetarian food and moving with new entities has ruined her life. The ideals and morals of India have been buried in alien soil.

Nina and Ananda never showed up to straighten things out. They continued to live together in a state of ego and misunderstanding, never feeling guilty. They continued their relationships with Anton and Mandy, respectively, despite the fact that neither was aware of the other's lie. Nina's sari was replaced with jeans and a t-shirt, and her hair colour was altered to yellow, and she was no longer in the cultural castle or religious taboo. Her senses are dominated by glitter and the flavour of western existence. She sacrifices her modesty only to be self-sufficient. She has now established herself as an excellent model of a western lady. When Nina learns of her mother's death, she goes through the most difficult period of her life. She visits India, watches the traditions, and recalls days spent with her mother, principles instilled in her, and the relationship she had with the country and its ideals, which moved her to tears. Nina avoided seeing her pals because she was consumed by guilt. Nina's identity was lost in the process of discovering a new way of life. She resolves not to commit the sin again before returning to Canada. In a diasporic topic, Manju Kapur has brilliantly captured the pride of Indian culture. She discovers a blond hair on her pillow shortly after her return from India, and the mystery of Ananda's relationship with Mandy is revealed. Nina takes some time to consider her options in life, and she wants to put a stop to their hide-and-seek game. Nina is bold and wants to get rid of all the filth, so she decides to start again, which Ananada does not like. Nina abandons her marriage and her life in the West. She starts looking for a position at the University of New Brunswick.

The author does not say if she will return to Halifax. Nina is a new lady who wants to start over and make amends for her previous errors. The reader must decide if she will be a Canadian, Indian, or global lady. All we know about Nina Kapur is that she undergoes a transformation, and like an eagle, she rediscovers her power and identity, allowing her to soar above all the immigrants who are still oppressed in a foreign place.

Conclusion

The idea of diaspora is threaded throughout Manju Kapur's work. This work vividly depicts the lives of immigrants and their difficulties in assimilating and adapting to their new surroundings. Immigrants confront a slew of issues when they arrive in a new country. They don't figure out a means to battle against all odds and remain unflappable. Instead, they see it as a chance to participate in the new world. They exist to survive, and their ability to do so is determined by their shifting attitudes. Every action they make to appease others around them ends in disaster. They do not fearlessly emerge from the misleading environment when they recognise their error or the identity they have lost in striving the new world. Nina boldly resolves to start a new life after realising her error. Her attitude shift, acceptance of the reality, and search for identity have all made a significant difference in her life. I conclude this article by stating that the notion of diaspora will persist until every immigrant's mentality changes.

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